

Building the collective at times of precarity:
precarious labour and its countermovements

A Conceptual Review of Precarity

Literature Report

Version 2.1

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Introduction

The present literature report was drafted as part of the theoretical framework of the project *COLLECTITUDE - Building the collective at times of precarity: precarious labour and its countermovements*.

Precarity is a prevalent phenomenon in capitalist countries and, at the same time, has become ubiquitous across the social sciences in order to understand the transformations of social and economic life, particularly since the 1980s, but with different timeframes and configurations across countries. However, “the question remains how this phenomenon should be understood conceptually” (Wright 2016, p. 127).

On the one hand, the proliferation of related terms – precarity, precariousness, precarisation, precarious work, precariat¹ – leads to a conceptual ambiguity over which one to adopt and which social and economic phenomena they are meant to analyse (Parfitt and Barnes 2020). On the other hand, the widespread use of the concept of “precarity”, at theoretical and political levels, often with a strong normative-ideological slant, and its understanding in very distinct ways have also led to an overstretching of the concept (Alberti et al. 2018), biasing the debate and contributing to the trivialisation of the term. It is necessary to specify its meaning, at the risk of losing its analytical purchase (Millar, 2017).

This paper intends to map major lines of thought along this debate, as well as to shed light on the framing of collective forms of workers organisation, from the perspective of their professional and economic activities, in response to precarisation processes.

The meanings and uses of precarity

The review of literature on precarity suggests that it continues to prove a valuable contribution to the study of contemporary labour and livelihoods (Mallett 2020, p. 271). Three major works that are consistently referenced across the literature on precarity define it in fundamentally different ways: Bourdieu (1998), its main precursor, presents it as a labour condition, Standing (2011) as a class category, and Butler (2004) as an ontological experience of human existence (Millar 2017).

Therefore, in approaching precarity, we should distinguish between a broad conception that recognises many dimensions and sites of precariousness in contemporary life and a narrow conception focused on specific labour relations and respective consequences. This double perspective has been defined as a “contrast between precarity-in-work and

¹ The word for the adjective “precarious” originates from Latin root *precor* (pray)/ *precarius* (obtained on condition of praying for), and in France it has been used since the 14th century. As a specific concept used to frame social problems, “*précarité*” first appeared in France in the late 1970s (Barbier 2002). In English, we find both the terms *precarity* and *precariousness*: *precarity* is used to “denote a structural condition tied in particular to work and the contract. Instead, ‘*precariousness*’ denotes an experiential condition to do with the person’s life as a quality inherent to that person and his/her specific positioning” (Armano and Murgia 2015, p. 104).

precarity-in-life” (Parfitt 2020). Narrower conceptions of precarity that restrict it to a limited set of dimensions or quantitative criteria, such as particular forms of employment, have the value of enhancing measurability and comparability, but miss more subjective perceptions and experiences of precarity that may be captured in a more qualitative way. Furthermore, precarity manifests different configurations according to specific national contexts, sectors of economic activities, professional fields, etc., requiring questioning which indicators to consider in each specific reality.

Precarity as a labour condition

Despite the variety of ways that the family of precarity-related terms may have been used in different national and cultural contexts, it has typically been related with "insecure, volatile, or vulnerable human situations that are socioeconomically linked to the labour-market dynamics" (Porta et al. 2015, p. 1).

In his early works on *The Algerians* (1962), Bourdieu already problematised how the ideas of full employment, unemployment and underemployment are relative to the cultural system, contrasting the perceptions of those who had a new system of reference derived from emigration experiences to France or to Algerian cities with those who remained in the traditional rural environment, as well as the feeling of (in)security associated with these different experiences. However, it was only in the 1990's that precarity emerged as an analytical concept when Bourdieu claimed that “precariety is now everywhere”:

(...) in the private sector, but also in the public sector, which has greatly increased the number of temporary, part-time or casual positions; in industry, but also in the institutions of cultural production and diffusion – education, journalism, the media, etc. In all these areas it produces more or less identical effects, which become particularly visible in the extreme case of the unemployed: the destructuring of existence, which is deprived among other things of its temporal structures, and the ensuing deterioration of the whole relationship to the world, time and space. (...) The existence of a large reserve army, which, because of the overproduction of graduates, is no longer restricted to the lowest level of competence and technical qualification, helps to give all those in work the sense that they are in no way irreplaceable and that their work and their jobs are in some way a privilege, a fragile, threatened privilege. (Bourdieu 1998, pp. 82–83)

In this perspective of precarity as a labour condition, Kalleberg, from the US context, defines precarious work as "employment that is uncertain, unpredictable, and risky from the point of view of the worker" (2009, p. 2). It is a phenomenon associated with the contraction of stable, waged, full-time jobs that characterise the so-called standard employment relations, and the increasing predominance of flexible work arrangements without steady incomes or adequate social protection or other rights normally provided to workers in an employment relation, commonly identified as the shift from Fordism to post-Fordism. However, as many authors have argued, this narrative can be misleading since Fordism has never been hegemonic worldwide and has excluded large segments of the populations even in the more advanced economies where it was more widespread (Palmer 2014), and particularly in specific sectors. Migrants, domestic workers, farmers, care workers, informal workers, unemployed, underemployed, have

always been less protected workers. Fordist full-time, stable and full employment has been a privilege of predominantly white men from western societies (Bonoli and Sarfati 2002; Lorey 2015). Even U.S. autoworkers, an iconic segment of the Fordist working class, have been pervaded by precarity and constant threats of layoff and relocation (Kasimir 2018). Therefore, different authors claim that Fordism has been the exception and precarity the norm (Kasimir 2018; Neilson and Rossiter 2008; Palmer 2014; van der Linden 2014). For Kasimir, precarisation does not mark a new circumstance of capitalist development, but it does indicate a turning point in terms of the "convergence of working lives in the Global North and South" (2018, p. 7). It is, in fact, strongly anchored in normative and ideological conceptions (see, for instance, Neilson & Rossiter, 2008, who frame it as a political concept).

According to Kalleberg (2009), precarity has existed since the launch of paid employment as a primary source of sustenance with the emergence of the market economy in the nineteenth century and is inseparable of the transformations of capitalism. Drawing on Polanyi (2001 [1944]), the author describes it in terms of a cyclical "double movement" between flexibility and security: in the 1930s and in the 2000s, free markets have led to demands for greater security, while in the 1970s regulated markets have led to demands by business for more flexibility, each phase with its specific characteristics, employment relations and managerial regimes:

Changes in employment relations reflect the transformations in managerial regimes and systems of control. The first Great Transformation was characterised by despotic regimes of control that relied on physical and economic coercion. The harsh conditions associated with the commodification of labour under market despotism led to a countermovement characterised by the emergence of hegemonic forms of control that sought to elicit compliance and consent (Burawoy 1979, 1983). The second Great Transformation has seen a shift to hegemonic despotism, whereby workers agree to make concessions under threat of factory closures, capital flight, and other forms of precarity... (Kalleberg 2009, p. 12).

He proposes that "a cohesive study of precarious work should build on the general concept of employment relations", which allows studying the connections between macro and micro levels of analysis "because they explicitly link individuals to the workplaces and other institutions wherein work is structured" (Kalleberg 2009, p. 12). In this respect, another crucial approach is to identify the broad social structures, institutions and organisations that manufacture and mediate precarity.

From a different perspective, Denning (2010) argues that wage labour should be decentred from our conception of capitalism: rather than the employment contract, "the imperative to earn a living" is the founding moment of capitalism. "You don't need a job to be a proletarian: wageless life, not wage labour, is the starting point in understanding the free market" (Denning 2010, p. 81). At stake is the separation of workers from their means of subsistence and an increasing dependence on monetary relations (see also Federici, 2009). The wage relation in one social relation among many arising from the imperative to earn a living. This acknowledgment contributes to reveal the ideological construction of wage labour as a normative livelihood model and of precarity as a novel phenomenon. Insecurity in labour and life is constitutive of capitalist development, inside and outside wage labour (Millar 2017). Precarious labour takes a

variety of forms and regimes, which is uneven across contexts (Breman 2013; Paret 2016).

Returning to narrower conception focused on specific labour relations, Kalleberg (2009) identifies a set of objective indicators of the growth of precarious work in the US: the general decline in the average length of time people spend with their employers; increase in long-term unemployment (defined as jobless for six months or more); growth in perceived job insecurity; growth of nonstandard work arrangements and 'contingent' work (upon employer's needs), such as subcontracting/ outsourcing and temporary work (part-time); and increase in risk-shifting from employers to employees – illustrated by the increase in defined contribution pension and health insurance plans (in which employees pay more of the premium and absorb more of the risk than do employers) and the decline in defined benefit plans (in which the employer absorbs more of the risk than the employee). It should be noted that bogus self-employment, though more difficult to capture objectively, is used by employers to disproportionately transfer risk to workers, therefore it is important to look at data on self-employed workers.

From a macro-institutional perspective, a report by the International Labour Organisation (ILO) (International Labour Office 2016) indicates that non-standard employment (NSE) comprises four different employment arrangements: (1) temporary employment (fixed-term contracts, including project-based or task-based contracts); (2) part-time work (including zero-hours contracts and on-call work); (3) multi-party employment relationship (temporary agency work, subcontracted labour, a without direct, subordinate relationship with end user); (4) disguised employment/ dependent self-employment (not part of an employment relationship). The report draws attention to the fact that not all NSE is precarious, as for some working in NSE is an explicit choice with positive outcomes, though for most workers it is indeed associated with precarity. In line with the above reasoning, the report argues that “rather than labelling non-standard employment as precarious, it is more useful to consider the insecurities that may be associated with any work – whether standard or non-standard” (p. 18), considering, similarly to Standing (2011), seven areas of potential work insecurity: (1) Employment insecurity – related to uncertainty regarding the continuity of employment and the risk of losing job; (2) Earnings' insecurity – as earnings are low, often not providing a “minimum living wage”, and uncertain with respect to future earnings; (3) Hours insecurity, whereas insufficient or too heavy-paced, leading to concerns over insufficient earnings, risks for workers' safety and health, and conflicts over work–life balance. In addition, certain scheduling patterns can also be an obstacle for interaction with unions or other workers and thus hinder representation of the workers' concerns; (4) Insecurity with respect to occupational safety and health – arising from workers not being sufficiently protected by OSH provisions that shield workers from hazards, work-related diseases and injuries, but also general conditions of work that can affect health and well-being; (5) Insecurity with respect to social security coverage – not having access, or having inadequate access, to social protection; (6) Insecurity with respect to training – not having access, or having inadequate access, to training opportunities that enhance professional development and career advancement; (7) Representation insecurity – concerning impediments faced by

workers in possessing a collective voice, being represented by a trade union and protected by collective agreements, and in exercising other fundamental principles and rights at work (freedom from discrimination in respect of employment and occupation, the elimination of forced or compulsory labour, abolition of child labour).

Furthermore, precarity also has cross-cutting and pervasive consequences that go beyond the labour market, from the individual to the structural level. Kalleberg (2009) identifies the main consequences of precarious work: greater economic inequality, insecurity, and instability, which in turn result in a growth in pessimism and a decrease in satisfaction with one's standard of living, and decrease in the opportunities for upward mobility; educational decisions are more precarious due to uncertainty and unpredictability of future work opportunities, as well as lack of income to invest in education; impact on individuals' health and stress; the experience of precarity also corrodes one's identity and promotes anomie, as argued by Sennett (1998); effects on families and households (less time available for the family, timing of marriage and children, as well as the number of children to have); effects on communities, as it may lead to a lack of social engagement, indicated by declines in membership in voluntary associations and community organisations, to uprooting of populations who move to where they can afford, or to negative attitudes toward immigrants; political outcomes by corroding stability, democratisation processes.

Therefore, Webster argues that precarity is a public issue and, as such, requires a diagnosis of the social structures and social institutions that manufacture it:

[W]hen large numbers of workers in different factories, in different countries, experience the same feelings of insecurity, it is no longer a personal trouble only, it is a public issue. To understand insecurity, it is not enough to identify the sense of helplessness, fear, depression, anger, and sadly, often self-destructive behaviour such as suicide, substance abuse and domestic violence. It is necessary, as Mills argued, to identify the broad social forces, institutions and organizations that manufacture this insecurity. (Webster et al. 2008, p. 3)

Millar (2017) also calls for a critical approach to precarity, referring to discussions that have arisen in recent years over the unintended ideological effects that the focus on precarity has produced, whether obscuring racial, class, and gender inequalities, North-South divides, or upholding normative ideals of "decent" work and wage labour that have long justified forms of discipline, exclusion, and exploitation. From her perspective, the "constant invoking of the term precarity might say less about the novelty of this condition than it does about hegemonic concerns over security and the attachment to privileges once held by certain populations" (p.7). In line with this perspective, precarity is seen as an instrument of governmentality (Lorey 2015) and a "mode of social control" in which "labour is disciplined by the threat of job loss and the uncertainty of employment prospects" (Doogan 2015).

Within this complexity, different authors argue for the notion of precarisation as a process, rather than a fixed condition. Mallett and Kingdom (2020) suggest that the concept of precarity should be understood as rooted in concrete labour market experiences but also connected to broader anxieties over social and political life; a process-focused concept rather than end-state descriptor; speaking to longer histories

and wider geographies than its commonplace status as a residual term or category implies. Porta et al. (2015) emphasise that precarisation involves highly complex and constantly evolving dynamics, "the common denominator of which cannot be easily captured" (p. 2), claiming that it should be approached as "a multi-dimensionally complex process being shaped not only by the non-linear dynamics of capitalism, but also by the actions, activities, and resistance of people living in precarious situations themselves – without forgetting how these two spheres are institutionally mediated in the specific circumstances under study" (p.3). Alberti et al. (2018) assess the strengths and limitations of using the concept of precarity as an analytical tool for examining the world of work, suggesting a focus on the drivers and patterns of precarisation as a process to describe increasing insecurity in both subjective and objective respects and the need to address precariousness in the realm of social reproduction and post-wage politics. They claim that "it is imperative to recognise precarity as an inherent condition of producers with capitalism on the one hand, while on the other also demanding more nuance in identifying the different processes through which precarity may increase across a diverse range of employment contexts" (Alberti 2018, p. 450). They identify different forms of precarisation: *explicit forms of precarisation*, mainly associated to particular contractual forms (temporary agency work, zero hour contracts, sub-contracting, gig work, dependent self-employment); *implicit precarisation*, related to an increasing sense of insecurity and fear and to the strategies to make individuals disposable vis-à-vis their organisational superiors, pertaining a disciplinary power; *citizenship precarisation*, in which the state, rather than employers, is the key manufacturer of precarisation, due to its ability to determine individuals' access to welfare and social protection; and *productive precarisation*, through processes of restructuring.

In the Portuguese context, the works of Carmo and colleagues (2021) provide an important contribution to the analysis of precarity as a process, focusing in their recent work on the pandemic crisis. They identify a trend in the Portuguese labour market towards increasing diversity and complexity of professional paths.

Within this precarity complex, any inquiry should consider it as a multi-dimensional process, operating at the macro, meso and micro levels, intertwined with capitalist development.

Precarity as a class

Guy Standing's influential book "The Precariat: The New Dangerous Class" (2011) has had a major contribution in drawing attention to the escalation of workers' insecurity around the globe, beyond North-South divides, opening up a controversial but prolific debate on precarity and class studies. According to Standing, precarity is still a labour condition, but his novelty is that precarious workers are defined as a new global class, more precisely a "class-in-the-making": the precariat – "a neologism that combines an adjective 'precarious' and a related noun 'proletariat'" (Standing 2011, p. 7). The term was first coined in Italy – *il precariato* – and strengthened as "a slogan by post-operait militants in Milan, organising casual workers in an alternative May Day protest in 2004" (Breman 2013, p. 134).

For Standing, the precariat is a "new dangerous class" who is distinct from the proletariat as it consists of people who have none of the social contract relationships of wage labour and are marginalised from the rights associated with "industrial citizenship", being defined by what it lacks: "seven forms of labour-related security" (labour market security; employment security; job security; work security; skill reproduction security; income security; representation security) (Standing, 2011, p. 10). The precariat "is not just a matter of having insecure employment, of being in jobs of limited duration and with minimal labour protection, although all this is widespread. It is being in a status that offers no sense of career, no sense of secure occupational identity and few, if any, entitlements to the state and enterprise" (Standing, 2011, p. 24). In a later work, Standing (2014) has defined *the precariat* based on ten features: (1) *Distinctive relations of production*, consisting of people living through insecure jobs and living insecurely, with uncertain access to housing and state supports; (2) *Distinctive relations of distribution*, which relates to the above-mentioned "imperative to earn a living" (Denning, 2010), lacking access to different kinds of social income (not only wage, but also company non-wage benefits, community benefits, state benefits, own-account production and income from other assets); (3) *Distinctive relations to the state*, as denizens who have a more limited range of citizenship and labour rights than citizens do; (4) *Lack of occupational identity*; (5) *Lack of control over time*, as they are exploited and oppressed by having to undertake a great deal of unpaid work and being expected to be available for work at any time; (6) *Detachment from labour*, as they are only intermittently or instrumentally involved in labour, without the feeling that the jobs they are doing are dignifying, tending to have a psychological detachment from labour; (7) *Low social mobility*; (8) *Over-qualification*, leading to status frustration and stress from underemployment; (9) *Uncertainty*, given their higher exposure to more spheres of uncertainty than other groups and their fewer rights and resources to deal with uncertainty and risk; (10) *Poverty and precarity traps*, that go beyond the workplace (p. 16-28).

This approach leads Standing (2014) to identify three varieties of precariat based on different experiences of deprivation: first, "people bumped out of working-class communities and families", with decreased status, skill and respect; second, the "traditional denizens – migrants, Roma, ethnic minorities, asylum seekers in limbo, all those with the least secure rights anywhere"; third "the educated, plunged into a precariat existence after being promised the opposite", which are defined by the deprivation related to the frustration of "having no future". For the author, this third group is more prone to a new progressive vision. The question, according to his analysis, is whether the three groups will be able to find a common identity, building solidarity across different contexts and conditions of precarity to form a class-for-itself (p.29-31).

Various scholars have challenged Standing's class-based approach to precarity. Munck (2013) criticises the Eurocentrism of approaching the precariat as a *new dangerous class*, since it does not acknowledge that "the type of work described by the term 'precarity' has always been the norm in the global South" (Munck 2013, p. 752) and has long been a part of global capitalist development.

Neilson and Rossiter (2008), analysing the highly diverse composition of precarity gathered around the sign of creative labour, contend that while precarity cuts across class and other divisions, it "can never (or, better, not alone) offer a new political subject" (Neilson 2008, p. 60).

According to a Marxist perspective, the precariat is formed mainly by the most exploited and dominated fractions of the working class (Braga 2016; Breman 2013). "The precarious situation of labour was recognised in the nineteenth century as a defining condition of proletarianisation, in the classic sense: stripped of the means of subsistence on the land, workers could only survive by selling their labour; the precariousness of their livelihood features in the Communist Manifesto" (Breman 2013, p. 134).

"the higher the productivity of labour, the greater is the pressure of the workers on the means of employment, the more precarious therefore becomes the condition for their existence, namely the sale of their own labour-power for the increase of alien wealth, or in other words the self-valorisation of capital." (Marx, 1990 [1867], p. 798)

This relates to Denning's (2010) perspective on the imperative to earn a living as the founding moment of capitalism, in face of the processes of dispossession and expropriation of land, tools and means of subsistence and the radical dependence on the market. Denning returns to Marx's concept of relative surplus population, in *Capital*: "Every worker belongs to it during the time when [s]he is only partially employed or wholly unemployed". Dialectically, the concept of "virtual pauper", developed in *Grundrisse*, points to the point of view of "living labour", considering that "since the exchange required for the means of living—the selling of labour-power—is accidental and indifferent to their organic presence, the worker is a virtual pauper" (Denning, 2010, p. 97).

Also, Erik Olin Wright (2016), whose work is a cornerstone for class studies, addresses this debate. He argues that the precariat is not a distinct class based on a basic criterion which is used in both the Marxist and Weberian traditions of class analysis to describe a social category as a class: material interests².

(...) to be constituted as a class distinct from the working class, the precariat must have material interests that are clearly differentiated from those of the working class. I will argue that this is not in general the case, whether we define material interests in terms of the opposition of capitalism versus socialism or in terms of alternative rules of the game of capitalism. Second, if we look more narrowly at material interests in terms of concrete strategies for securing a livelihood within the existing rules of the game, then people within a given class should share broadly similar optimal strategies. In the case of the precariat, the different segments identified by Standing have sharply different strategies of survival and advancement. The precariat is thus neither a class in terms of the differentiation of class interests from workers, or in terms of the unity of interests across its segments. (Wright 2016, p. 123)

Given the complexity of contemporary class structures, a binary view of the class relations of capitalism as consisting only of capitalists and workers would be too

² Wright elucidates the criterion for what constitutes material interests: "for any given person it is possible to identify actions and social changes which would improve or harm their material conditions of life" (Wright, 2016, p. 129).

simplistic. Wright proposes to locate the interests connected to precarious workers in the complex class structures of capitalism analysed at more concrete levels of analysis, wherein the concept of contradictory locations within class relations (Wright 1985, 2000) is already comprehensively conceptualised:

The precariat is either a part of the working class if class is analysed in terms of the basic rules of the game of twentieth-century developed capitalism, or it is itself an aggregation of several distinct class locations if class is defined narrowly in terms of homogeneous interests defined by moves in the game. The precariat, as a rapidly growing segment of the working class and the bearer of the sharpest grievances against capitalism, may have a particularly important role to play in struggles over the rules of capitalism and over capitalism itself, but it is not a class in its own right. (Wright, 2016, pp. 134–135)

The material conditions of life for both the precariat and the working class within capitalism “would be enhanced in an alternative economy built around various forms of social ownership, democratic empowerment over broad investment priorities, an expansive sector of decommodified public goods, a cooperative form of market relations, and the other components of democratic socialism” (Wright 2016, p. 132).

Despite varied social conditions and insecurities, and contradictory class locations, the precarity of capitalist work, inside and outside wage labour, seems to frame a common class regime.

[A relational approach: from precarity-in-work to precarity-in-life](#)

Based on the experiences that are voiced by people facing events of precarisation, Porta et al. emphasise that “precarity and precarisation, above all, mean the colonisation of life by market forces – be these in the form of commodity markets, financial markets, labour markets, real estate markets, agricultural markets, law markets, or academic market” (Porta et al., 2015, p. 10).

From this perspective, a growing body of literature conceptualises precarity has an ontological experience of human existence, not limited to work arrangements. The writing of philosopher and gender theorist Judith Butler is a main reference for such approach. Her work (2004), in the aftermath of September 11, 2001, relates precariousness to a common condition of vulnerability that pervades human existence by virtue of events that are outside one's control. This has been again exposed at the turn of the 2020s, in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, that demonstrates the extent to which the human community is equally precarious and dependant on anonymous others (Butler 2020). However, some peoples are particularly disposable and dispensable:

There is short-term work or no work at all, or post-Fordist forms of flexible labour that rely on the substitutability and dispensability of working peoples. These developments, bolstered by prevailing attitudes toward health insurance and social security, suggest that market rationality is deciding whose health and life should be protected and whose health and life should not. (Butler 2015, p. 11)

As such, Butler looks at precarisation as a process that extends beyond a labour condition. “Usually induced and reproduced by governmental and economic

institutions, this process acclimatises populations over time to insecurity and hopelessness" and is built not only into the institutions of temporary labour, but also "of decimated social services and the general attrition of the active remnants of social democracy in favour of entrepreneurial modalities supported by fierce ideologies of individual responsibility and the obligation to maximise one's own market value as the ultimate aim in life" (2015, p. 15). The author calls for the need of an understanding of precarity as, on the one hand, a structure of affect since it instigates "a change in psychic reality", an existential state; and, on the other, a feature of the failures and inequalities of the socioeconomic and political system, since the experiences of vulnerability and social and economic deprivation (such as unemployment or lack of shelter) reveal a political economy that fails to safeguard against those experiences (2015, p. 22).

In the French context, the notion of '*precarité*' first appeared precisely in the field of social policies, with a meaning associated with persisting poverty and exclusion as multidimensional phenomena and the related emergence of 'insertion policies' for the most vulnerable (Paugam 1993), before being more specifically associated to a labour condition (Barbier 2002). In earlier works, Bourdieu already called attention to the fact that the creation of a generalised and permanent state of insecurity is part of "a mode of domination of a new kind" which forces workers into submission and into acceptance of exploitation (Bourdieu 1998, p. 85). Though presented as an economic system, this is, in reality, "a political system which can only be set up with the active or passive complicity of the officially political powers" (Bourdieu, 1998, p. 86).

Drawing on Butler's ontological conception, Millar (2017) explains that it inspired two uses of the term precarity. A set of studies extend the meaning of precarity beyond labour as a synonym for vulnerability or insecurity, as something we are likely to find everywhere, hence which "run the risk of losing precarity's analytical purchase, rooted in the analysis of specific labour conditions" (p. 4). Other set of works have sought to develop a relational approach, bridging the notion of ontological precarity with an analysis of specific labour regimes and political-economic structures, hence "linking the study of political economy with questions of culture, subjectivity, psychological interiority, and lived experience" (p. 5). That is the case of Neilson and Rossiter (2008) who show that "precarity is an ontological experience and social-economic condition with multiple registers that hold the potential to contribute to a political composition of the common" (p. 58).

Millar argues that a relational approach to precarity also allows to grasp it not as a fixed empirical object but as a method of inquiry that questions "how precarious labour and precarious life intersect in particular times and places". Its answer lies in considering the sociological analysis of precarity but also the political work that this concept performs" (Millar 2017, p. 5), illuminating as well how it is experienced across social positions and in different subjectivities:

For some, precarity certainly describes an experience of loss. But for others, it might constitute a refusal of waged work, an alternative political subjectivity, or a mode of life that does not conform to liberal ideals. (Millar 2017, p. 7)

From a cultural anthropology perspective, Kasmir (2018) notes the relevance of the structures of emotion and subjectivity associated with precarious

lifeworlds, “exploring disenfranchisement, displacement, and uncertainty”. This perspective calls into question the notion of everyday routines, as there is little regularity in such context of uncertainty.

A relational approach also contribute to the goal of decentring precarity from wage labour (Kasimir 2018) and to entail a feminist critique, raising the visibility of women’s unpaid work, as performed by Lorey (2015) through the lens of biopolitics, or by Pulignano (2019) who rethinks "precariousness" in terms of the paid-unpaid continuum of work.

Pulignano defines precariousness as resulting from subjective conditions (e.g. exhaustion, mental and physical health) and objective conditions (e.g. unsocial working hours, low or no pay) that "pose difficulties to people when planning for the future across the spectrum of their work and life" (Pulignano 2019, p. 6). The author shows how unpaid activities increasingly underlie paid employment as a source of value creation in a deregulated labour market. Unpaid work, defined as “unremunerated work within formal (paid) employment”, expresses the ongoing changes in labour markets, whereby “unpaid work has gradually lost its original purpose of being solely concerned with social reproduction” (Pulignano 2019, p. 5). Drawing on contemporary sociological theories, she argues for overcoming the traditional categorical dichotomy between productive and reproductive work, which also relates to the sociological debates on (de)commodification and politics of value (Appadurai 1986). In fact, work that is commodified and monetised (paid) is valued, whereas work that is separated from the commodity dimension underpinning the market logic and is unpaid is "not considered to be work, and therefore is not valued" (Pulignano 2019, p. 7). This is reflected in common economic measures of national growth (i.e., the Gross National Product) that do not account for unpaid work and in the non-valuation of domestic and care work, which is still largely carried out by women. Federici (2009) provides an account of the genesis of the separation of production from reproduction, in which domestic work is key, not only in the exploitation of women in capitalism, but also as part of the (re)production of labour power, by daily regenerating workers capacity to work.

Pulignano’s agenda calls for the urge to analyse the extent to which and how unpaid work contributes to precariousness by developing a view of precariousness that encompasses different socio-economic modes and forms of work. Her analytical framework identifies three dimensions underpinning objective and subjective precariousness within the continuum of paid and unpaid work to operationalise precariousness as the social and economic unpredictability that individuals face with regard to their own future: (1) *(In)voluntary work*, which is the extent to which individuals perceive unpaid work as necessary for securing and/or sustaining paid work (e.g. artists undertaking unpaid work as a means of improving their career prospects); (2) *Control over work*, corresponding to the extent to which individuals can exercise control over their work content and working conditions (e.g. the self-employed, whose employment status should allow them control over their work schedule, undertake unpaid work as a means of gaining more clients); and (3) *Economic dependency*, as the extent to which income and the social protections inherent to each employment arrangement within different national regulatory contexts protect individuals against

social risk, thereby reducing their propensity to undertake unpaid work (Pulignano 2019, pp. 15–16). This heuristic framework further acknowledges the intersection with the social categories of gender, age and ethnicity, so that segmentation between good and bad jobs in the labour markets unveils "in-depth social fissures among different social groups within society" (Pulignano 2019, p. 17).

Drawing on Pulignano's framework, the extent to which and how the undercutting of paid employment may involve or lead to the creation of unpaid tasks (traineeships, preparatory work, spending time establishing an online presence, engaging in lengthy efforts applying to calls and competing for projects often in vain, working unsocial hours, searching for tasks) is a relevant theoretical and empirical question for a relational approach to precarity.

Tackling, organising, and resisting precarity

Considering that precarity has existed since the emergence of the market economy in the nineteenth century and is constitutive of capitalism, associated to the radical dependence on the market as a primary source of sustenance (Denning 2010; Kalleberg 2009; Millar 2017), it also relies on the role of counterforces, namely in contesting the market hegemony (Porta *et al.*, 2015). These include the social state, socioeconomic and political institutions, and collective organisations that support different forms of solidarity.

The common experiences of individual vulnerability and the understanding that this situation is shared have the potential to reveal that precarity is socially produced and implicated in a broader social world and, therefore, to engender collective responses to tackle precarity, as argued by Butler:

This initiates the possibility of taking apart that individualising and maddening form of responsibility in favour of an ethos of solidarity that would affirm mutual dependency, dependency on workable infrastructures and social networks, and open the way to a form of improvisation in the course of devising collective and institutional ways of addressing induced precarity. (Butler 2015, pp. 21–22)

As such, we also need a better understanding of the factors that influence personal and collective agency and its forms, as well as of new models of organising and strategies of mobilisation that are likely to be effective in light of increased precarity (Kalleberg, 2009). In this section, we briefly overview debates on the collective action of precarious workers, that is, their political mobilisation and collective representation, as well as on the collective forms of workers organisation, from the perspective of their professional and economic activities, in response to precarisation processes.

Political mobilisation and representation

A substantial body of literature addresses how precarious work faces the issue of precarious organising given the limited co-presence of workers in a common workplace, challenging traditional institutions of workers' representation, works councils and

unions (Fichter and Sydow, 2013) and, more broadly, the centrality of work in the development of solidarity and social citizenship (Castel 2009). Trade unions, with generally limited membership among more precarious workers, have been accused of not representing the interests of “these so-called outsiders”, though in the past two decades they have been increasingly attempting to tackle precariousness (Keune and Pedaci 2020).

Heery and Abbott (2002) review the different approaches unions have developed to protect existing members from insecurity and extend union organisation to the more insecure, identifying five types of responses to insecurity (exclusion, servicing, partnership, social dialogue and mobilisation). They argue that, on the one hand, “the changing structure of the workforce poses a serious threat to unions because insecure workers are difficult to organise and represent”, but, on the other hand, “growing insecurity may stimulate employee demand for union protection and provide unions with a representative opportunity” (Heery 2002, p. 155).

Kalleberg notes that, whether the workplace has lost its centrality in workers’ identities and political mobilisation, occupations are becoming important sources of affiliation and identification and are “useful concepts for describing the institutional pathways by which workers can organise to exercise their collective agency across multiple employers” (Kalleberg, 2009, 14). The entertainment industry trade union Equity is one of the few longstanding examples of a union that organises contingent workers as core members (Dean 2012).

In line with the above-mentioned debates on precarity and class, some scholars, like Standing (2011, 2014), have attempted to frame precarious workers as a new political subject, which would have its own forms of collective organisation and representation, while others have objected the formulation of the precariat as a collective political actor (Breman 2013; Neilson 2008). Before the variety of precarious labour regimes, what is at stake is the question of solidarity: to what extent collective actors with different vulnerabilities, identities and resources are able to develop strategies that underline their commonalities and forge common struggles, instead of seeing each other as rivals (Paret, 2016; Breman, 2013).

(...) because precarious labour is the norm of capitalist production and reproduction (or, better, the norm that blurs the boundaries between capitalist production and reproduction), it might contribute to the invention of new forms of political organisation that stretch across the divisions and apartheid established by the speeded-up and flexible conditions of contemporary capitalist accumulation. (...) At stake is a rethinking of the very notions we use to describe and analyse the current hierarchisation and spatialisation of labour, notions such as the international division of labour or the three worlds model of world geography (and its more contemporary binary elaborations, such as North/South). There is also a need to build precarity into the very solutions and alliances that might emerge from a practical rethinking of these notions: the construction of unstable institutions or organised networks from which to contest the current waves of capitalist development. In short, what is required is the acknowledgement and building of commonalities across the diverse situations in which labour is at work and on the move in the world today. (Neilson 2008, p. 58)

The commonalities forging common struggles has been evidenced, for instance, during the Covid-19 pandemic, through which precarious workers have been mobilising in different ways, from virtual mobilisation during lockdown to gradually occupying the public space. At the same time, existing tensions have been exposed "between the radical character of collective action that aims at dramatizing an unbearable condition, the need for bargaining, as well as the need for immediate relief in terms of material conditions or legal support" (Porta 2015, p. 17).

Recognising the contribution of precarious workers movements to contemporary labour struggles, Millar's (2017) critique of the politics of precarity calls for the need to unveil the conservative political effects of precarity, upon normative ideals of "decent" work and wage labour that justify forms of discipline, exclusion, and exploitation. Instead of approaching precarity as being the exception in capitalism, it holds great potential, not only at the analytical but also the political level, in being framed as "the necessary condition for the creation of capital", while also recognising that "wage labour can itself be an experience of insecurity, degradation, exploitation, and abuse" (p. 6). For Millar, drawing on Barchiesi (2012), the concept holds its greatest political potential in problematising the centrality of work and its progressive promise under capitalism and, we may add, in revealing its normative and ideologic bias.

Such problematisation might also lead to de-coupling welfare protection from employment:

There is an urgent need for a research agenda committed to more robust and empirical engagement which reflects the complexity of social protection in the current moment of contemporary capitalism. Greater theoretical insights into the ways in which social protections can reconcile productivist and reproductivist or anti-work perspectives are urgently needed. A key research agenda amongst work and employment scholars must be to generate more empirically grounded and politically imaginative ways of rethinking the security of people, which is delinked from their capacity to produce surplus value. These must also be better able to support existing concrete struggles fighting precarity inside and outside the workplace, and to regain ground for establishing radical alternative futures. (Alberti 2018, p. 454)

Whereas the distinctiveness and politics of precarity are not resolved, it is also important, as argued by Kasmir (2018), to map the range of livelihood activities people take up, the identities diverse labourers advance, alliances they pursue, organisational forms they innovate, and to map the scale of these affiliations. That is also the purpose of the *Collectitude* project in analysing collective forms of work organisation.

Collective forms of work and production organisation

Since the industrial revolution and the advent of market economy, worker-owned cooperatives and other forms of social economy have emerged to respond to people's needs in face dispossession of means of subsistence, exploitation of the working class, and proliferation of situations of poverty and marginalization, which neither the free market nor the family were able to address. The working classes have initiated different attempts to collectively and democratically address their needs from a perspective of

social transformation (Estivill and Dalmau 2019), which is nowadays broadly framed under the Social and Solidarity Economy (SSE) movement.

It is true that cooperative forms of associated labour long predate the capitalist era, as Vieta (2010) reminds us, providing pre-modern examples such as "groups practicing collaborative production and mutual aid, the economic life of the commons, and the social organisation of many indigenous communities". However, considering the modern era, the oldest vision for an emancipatory alternative to capitalism is the worker-owned cooperative (Wright 2010). Different cooperative experiments have emerged since the nineteenth century, especially drawing on the theories and experiences of utopian socialists and anarchists (Saint-Simon, Fourier, Owen, Proudhon, Buchez, Kropotkin, Landauer). These experiments kept flourishing throughout the 20th century in diverse socio-political contexts, notably as an alternatives to centrally planned or capitalist modes of production, distribution, and consumption, and in the late 1960s particularly associated with "broader social and economic demands for self-determination and workers' control around the concept of *autogestión* (self-management)" (Vieta 2010, p. 2).

As a broad concept for framing these varied collective initiatives, the SSE may be defined as "an alternative way of directly organizing economic activity that is distinct from capitalist market production, state organized production, and household production. Its hallmark is the production organized by collectivities directly to satisfy human needs not subject to the discipline of profit-maximization or state-technocratic rationality" (Wright 2010, pp. 140–141). In addition, these collectives, in line with their identity and values, tend to embrace a set of principles related to democratic member control, collective ownership, and social mission.

There is, however, is little research assessing the working conditions and the quality of jobs in the cooperative and SSE sector. Recent studies by CECOP (2019) and Eurofound (2019) provide important contributions to address this knowledge gap, focusing on specific case studies from European countries.

The study by CECOP (2019) has shown how workers use different cooperative models to provide responses to the challenges raised by non-standard employment, such as: worker cooperatives; social cooperatives, focused on vulnerable people often at the margins of the labour market; shared service cooperatives; new cooperative models for independent workers (freelancers); and emerging platform cooperativism (oriented toward collective and democratic ownership of digital services). These different models have been a laboratory for experimenting innovative and sustainable forms of work and employment, though they also face challenges related to precarious employment:

(...) some worker-members have non-standard employment contracts due to various reasons, such as an insufficient business capacity of the cooperative, members' personal situations, institutional barriers etc. In some cases, a worker cooperative is created as a project with weak business capacity at the beginning and members can work in the cooperative only as part-time or as independent workers who have to have other jobs in order to earn a living. (CECOP 2019, p. 20)

The study also calls attention to the fact that cooperative responses "should not relieve national governments of their responsibilities to find institutional solutions such as guaranteeing access to adequate social protection to all workers" (CECOP 2019, p. 42)

The Eurofound study (2019) on cooperatives and social enterprises, focused on five case study organisations in five European countries (Italy, Poland, Spain, Sweden and the United Kingdom), has shown employment resilience or even growth between the 2008 financial crisis to 2018, while also resisting to restructuring of employment towards more part-time jobs or temporary jobs. Regarding job quality, this study examines six dimensions based on the state-of-the-art and empirical work: (1) working time and work–life balance; (2) skills and task discretion; (3) social environment; (4) prospects in terms of recruitment, career and job security; (5) pay; and (6) voice and representation.

Regarding working time, given the “moral” or activist principles of these organisations, there is an assumption or expectation that workers work long hours and have poorer work–life balance. However, most workers interviewed for the study believed that “their working hours fitted in with their family or social commitments outside work” and gave positive assessments when comparing to their previous experiences in or knowledge of other organisations.

In what concerns skills and task discretion, a key aspect, according to the study, is providing workers with the skills that underpin their ability to take greater responsibility and autonomy within their work. On the one hand, the long-term relationships with their members and the reinvestment of surpluses into the cooperative enable to invest in the long-term skills development of workers. On the other hand, due to limited resources, these organisations experience problems providing training for workers. Among the study interviewees, a large majority of workers believed their skills development opportunities were "better" or "much better" than those in other organisations, also serving to underpin workers’ task autonomy.

Regarding the social environment, most interviewed workers expressed the opinion that their line managers and co-workers are encouraging and supportive, being "better" or "much better” than those in other organisations.

In terms of career prospects and job security, the fact of being part of a worker-member organization creates a longer-term perspective for both workers and managers, who emphasise personal skills and career development. However, at the same time, low staff turnover tends to present a challenge in terms of career opportunities. In addition, “job security in cooperatives is obtained by adjusting working hours and wages when faced with adverse conditions” (Eurofound 2019, p. 39).

Regarding pay, evidence for worker cooperatives and social enterprises is mixed: in some countries, studies suggest that workers in these organisations are paid more than mainstream business organisations; in other countries, they are paid relatively less. What is more consistent is that "the internal wage hierarchy (that is, the differential between the highest and lowest paid) in worker cooperatives is narrower than in mainstream organisations” (Eurofound 2019, p. 40).

Finally, regarding voice and representation, interviewed workers tended to feel engaged in decision-making processes and a large majority considered their current organisation

was "better" or "much better" than other organisations in this respect (Eurofound 2019, p. 41).

This exploratory approach to collective forms of work and production organisation shows that, though envisioning emancipatory alternatives, they are part of the same precarity complex, therefore should be further inquired within the critical and relational approach outlined here.

Final Remarks

This literature review aims to contribute to new theoretical, analytical and empirical approaches to work and precarity, considering it as a multi-dimensional and relational process, operating at the macro, meso and micro levels. At the same time, it contributes to the critical questioning of the status of work, in its different forms (productive or reproductive, formal or informal, paid or unpaid, market or socially oriented), in contemporary capitalist societies.

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